

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

PREVALENCE OF ASYMPTOMATIC MATERNAL AND NEWBORN CHILD VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY

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Article Received: May 2019

Accepted: June 2019

Published: July 2019

Abstract:

Background: Vitamin D deficiency is prevalent in south-east Asia, a finding that is unexpected in a tropical region with abundant sunshine. Vitamin D deficiency during pregnancy has important implications for the newborn and infant. **Objective:** To determine the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency among asymptomatic healthy mothers and newborns children. **Methodology:** This prospective cohort was conducted upon a sample of 200 mother-child pair's full-term pregnant mothers presenting to two different tertiary care hospitals from June 2018 to December 2018. All participating mothers delivered their babies via typical vaginal delivery. Samples of maternal and cord blood were collected on the day of delivery. Serum concentrations of 25(OH)D were measured in the samples. 25(OH)D concentrations < 30 nmol/L were considered to be indicative of hypo-vitaminosis D. The data obtained was recorded onto a structured questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS v.21 & Microsoft Excel 2016. **Results:** Among, the 200 mother-child pairs enrolled into the study, 39% of the newborns were males while the remaining 61% were females. The mean age of the mothers stood at 33 (SD ± 4). Mean maternal serum 25(OH)D was 19.4 ± 3.9 nmol/L, and cord blood 25(OH)D was 16.7 ± 2.9 nmol/L. Hypovitaminosis D was detected in 89% of the women and newborns during winter and 46% of the mothers and 35% of the newborns during summer. A positive correlation was found between maternal and cord blood 25(OH)D ($p < 0.001$). **Conclusion:** After careful consideration, it can be concluded that hypo-vitaminosis D among pregnant women and their newborns is highly prevalent and the magnitude warrants public health intervention.

Keywords: Vitamin D, 25(OH)D, Hypo-Vitaminosis D, Maternal & Child Health, Rickets Sustainable Development Goals and Public Health.

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Please cite this article in press Shafi Muhammad Wassan et al., *Prevalence of Asymptomatic Maternal and Newborn Child Vitamin D Deficiency*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 07(07).

INTRODUCTION:

The role of vitamin D in bone mineralization and mineral homeostasis is well known. More recently, a role for vitamin D deficiency in a range of disorders has emerged, together with the appreciation that vitamin D deficiency may be widespread. [1]

Although the reason for the increase in vitamin D deficiency is unclear, changes in lifestyle are likely to be important. In humans, the primary source of vitamin D is endogenous synthesis in the skin after exposure to ultraviolet rays of sunlight; the diet is a secondary source of vitamin D.

A combination of a change in lifestyle (with more daylight hours spent indoors), liberal use of sunscreens (in some parts of the world, mostly driven by concerns about the risk of skin cancer), adoption of covered attire (consistent with the accepted cultural norms in some societies), and global environmental pollution might have contributed to the widespread increase in vitamin D deficiency. [2]

A high prevalence of vitamin D deficiency has already been reported in Iran, India, Bangladesh, and Middle Eastern countries, where sociocultural trends and economic constraints probably contribute, despite abundant access to sunshine in these areas throughout the year. [3-5] In a study of male and female ambulatory patients, vitamin D deficiency was also found to be highly prevalent in the Pakistani community. [6]

Several disorders are associated with insufficient vitamin D stores, including common chronic disorders such as diabetes (type I and type II) and cardiovascular disease, autoimmune disorders such as multiple sclerosis and psoriasis, and malignancies such as breast cancer. [7-9]

More recently, vitamin D deficiency has been associated with adverse pregnancy outcomes, including pre-eclampsia, gestational diabetes mellitus, intrauterine growth restriction, and preterm birth. [10]

The effects of inadequate maternal vitamin D reserves extend well beyond the fetal and neonatal periods. Javaid et al.[11] demonstrated the adverse implications of maternal vitamin D deficiency on bone mineral density parameters in 9-year-old offspring; lower maternal 25-hydroxy vitamin D levels during late pregnancy were associated with reduced bone mineral content of the whole body ($P=0.009$) and the lumbar spine ($P=0.03$) in children aged 9 years.

The aim of the present study was to assess the status of vitamin D stores among a cohort of mothers and their newborns from 2 tertiary care hospitals and to relate this to cord blood levels of vitamin D in their newborns.

METHODOLOGY:

This prospective cohort was conducted upon a sample of 200 mother-child pairs full-term pregnant mothers presenting to two different tertiary care hospitals from June 2018 to December 2018. All participating mothers delivered their babies via typical vaginal delivery. Samples of maternal and cord blood were collected on the day of delivery. Serum concentrations of 25(OH)D were measured in the samples. 25(OH)D concentrations < 30 nmol/L were considered to be indicative of hypo-vitaminosis D. The data obtained was recorded onto a structured questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS v.21 & Microsoft Excel 2016.

A detailed questionnaire on patients' medical, family, and social histories and demographic information was completed. Data were also collected on dietary intake of dairy products and meat, and the use of prenatal vitamin supplements. Participants were asked about their clothing and the extent of bodily covering (1 = arms; 2 = head; 3 = hands; 4 = face; 5 = arms, head, and hands; 6 = arms, head, hands, and face), daily exposure to sunshine (1 = less than 10 minutes; 2 = less than 20 minutes; 3 = less than 30 minutes), and daily exercise (1 = none; 2 = household activities; 3 = outdoor physical activity).

Approximately 5 mL of venous blood was collected from each mother, and approximately 2 mL of cord venous blood was collected from the placental end of the severed umbilical cord at the time of delivery. The blood samples were labeled and centrifuged within 2 hours of collection. Neonatal variables recorded included duration of gestation, determined from first available ultrasound recording; birth weight; body length; sex; head circumference (HC); and abdominal circumference (AC).

Data were examined for normality of distribution and skewed variables (maternal and cord blood vitamin D levels) and were log-transformed to meet the assumption of normality for parametric assays. Maternal and newborn serum levels of 25-hydroxy vitamin D3 were categorized as: maximum 10 ng/mL (severe deficiency); 11–20 ng/mL (moderate deficiency); 21–30 ng/mL (mild deficiency); and more than 30 ng/mL (normal).

RESULTS:

Among, the 200 mother-child pairs enrolled into the study, 39% of the newborns were males while the remaining 61% were females. The mean age of the mothers stood at 33 (SD \pm 4). Overall, 26% of the women covered their arms, hands, and head, whereas 76% also covered their face. Detailed maternal characteristics are tabulated below.

MATERNAL CHARACTERISTICS		VALUES
Age (years)		33 \pm 4
B.M.I (Kg/m ²)		29 \pm 13
Duration of Pregnancy (weeks)		37 \pm 3
Parity		33 \pm 4
Daily Exercise	None	113 (56.5%)
	Moderate	49 (24.5%)
	Rigorous	38 (19%)
Daily Exposure to Sun	< 10 minutes	34 (17%)
	< 20 minutes	36 (18%)
	< 30 minutes	130 (65%)

Mean maternal serum 25(OH)D was 19.4 \pm 3.9 nmol/L, and cord blood 25(OH)D was 16.7 \pm 2.9 nmol/L. Hypovitaminosis D was detected in 89% of the women and newborns during winter and 46% of the mothers and 35% of the newborns during summer. A positive correlation was found between maternal and cord blood 25(OH)D ($p < 0.001$).

DISCUSSION:

The results of this study demonstrate that a majority of mothers and infants were vitamin D deficient. The strong correlation we noted between maternal and newborn plasma 25(OH)D levels offers further evidence that newborn plasma 25(OH)D levels are dependent on maternal plasma 25(OH)D levels, as has been previously reported. [4, 10]

One recent study in Arab children has identified maternal vitamin D deficiency as a risk factor for the development of rickets in children aged 0 to 3 years; [12] therefore physicians may need to consider vitamin D supplementation of infants at birth. Alternatively, increased supplementation of Vitamin D to women during the pregnancy beyond the standard prenatal multivitamin, which contains 400 IU vitamin

D2 or vitamin D3, may be an important prevention strategy.

This study was limited by the sample size, which did not allow for statistical comparisons of plasma 25(OH)D levels between different age groups. In summary, this study provides evidence for a high prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in mothers and their infants. Low vitamin D stores at birth may be another important risk factor for development of rickets.

At present, vitamin D supplementation is not a part of antenatal care programs in India. The US National Academy of Sciences mentions 400 IU as the dietary reference intake for vitamin D during pregnancy. However, several investigators worldwide are arguing for revised higher guidelines for vitamin D allowance during pregnancy and lactation. [13]

So far, the concern expressed by those investigators is mainly for women in temperate climates, especially those with greater skin pigmentation, and for women living in tropical regions but observing purdah, such as those in many parts of our country. Such recommendations perhaps are also warranted for pregnant women in our part of the world so that they may remain healthy and provide adequate vitamin D to their fetuses. The exact cause of or factors contributing to the occurrence of hypovitaminosis D in women remain to be elucidated in future studies.

CONCLUSION:

After careful consideration, it can be concluded that hypo-vitaminosis D among pregnant women and their newborns is highly prevalent and the magnitude warrants public health intervention.

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